

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Sales in Indonesia Private Hospitals

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ABSTRACT: The study explores marketing strategies for increasing sales of oncology-based medical equipment in private hospitals in Indonesia. Using qualitative methods, the research analyzes internal and external factors influencing purchasing decisions. The study highlights the importance of product quality, pricing strategies, and after-sales support. Recommendations include product differentiation, improved after-sales support, and participation in local medical events. These strategies are aimed at enhancing the market position of PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia in the competitive landscape of Indonesian private hospitals.

KEYWORDS: Competitor Analysis, External Analysis, Internal Analysis, Indonesia Private Hospitals, Marketing Mix, Pricing Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Purpose of this research is to examine the marketing strategies to penetrate Indonesia private hospitals for the oncology-based medical equipment. The primary objective is to understand the factors influencing the decision-making process of private hospitals before the decision is made. The research utilizes a qualitative methodology, incorporating primarily data from the respondents who are working in private hospitals with extensive experiences. The findings highlight the key issues related to product quality, pricing strategies, the purchasing process, and after-sales support. The study identifies the internal and external factors affecting the market through comprehensive frameworks such as the VRIO analysis, Porter's Five Forces, and SWOT analysis. The research underscores the significance of high-quality products and the need for streamlined processes to enhance customer satisfaction. Recommendations for PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia include focusing on product differentiation, improving after-sales support, adopting flexible pricing strategies, and increasing participation in local medical events. The study concludes that by addressing these areas, the company can strengthen its market position and increase sales in the competitive landscape of Indonesian private hospitals.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Marketing Strategy

According to Harvard Business Review (HBR), strategy implementation is the process of converting strategic initiatives into action to achieve company's goals and its objectives. This involves translating the strategic plans and decisions made at the organizational level into concrete actions and initiatives that are executed at the operational level. Marketing Strategy is one of the interconnected approaches besides business strategy under the strategic formulation which aims to communicate the planned trajectory of a business.

Marketing Mix

Marketing mix is a set of tools used in a company to achieve goals in carrying out marketing strategies towards potential customers. Marketing Mix 7P is a variable that can be used by a company with the aim of influencing customers from Segments that meet the company's criteria (Putri & Nuralam, 2024). In the initial explanation of this concept, this concept was known as the marketing mix or 4P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion). However, over time, the marketing mix concept has developed into 7Ps, namely Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, Physical Evidence (Natalia, 2023).

These seven elements make the marketing mix concept more complex because they take into account aspects that go beyond the characteristics of the product itself. The marketing component in the marketing mix is an important element that can influence the level of sales in a company. The marketing mix consisting of product, price, promotion and distribution has a significant impact on consumer behavior. The relationship between the four elements in the marketing mix is interrelated and influences each other. In

other words, every aspect has an impact on the company's overall marketing strategy and sales results (Muhammad Ihsan & Safira, 2020).

According to Poluan & Karuntu (2022) the marketing mix consists of dependent variables that are adjusted to produce the expected responses from the sample. The main objective of a marketing strategy is to provide offers by promoting and distributing products with the hope that the process of purchasing the product or service will continue. The variables identified by Kotler and Keller (2016) from the current marketing mix are the 7Ps (product, price, promotion, place, people, process, physical evidence).

On the other hand, there is a technique known as marketing mix adjustment in this regard, namely where the manufacturer adjusts each component of the marketing mix for each unique sale. The variables included in the marketing mix can be used effectively if they are adapted to the needs and challenges that a particular business is currently facing.

From the definition above, it can be seen that the determining factors of the marketing mix are factors that are evaluated and can be used by marketing managers to influence consumer purchasing decisions. These factors include, but are not limited to, people, procedures, place, price, product, and tangibles.

STP (Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning)

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) is a fundamental strategic framework employed by businesses to optimize their marketing efforts and enhance their competitive advantage in the marketplace (Kotler et al., 2020). This approach explains that the customization of marketing strategies to specific groups of consumers with similar characteristics is required because not all customers have having same characters.

External Analysis

The strategic management frameworks are used to analyze the various aspects of a business environment in conducting this research such as General Environment (Political/Legal, Demography, Sociocultural, Global, Physical, Technology, and Economic), Industry (Porter's Five Forces), and Competitor Analysis (Assumption, Objective, Strategy and Capability). These frameworks become the crucial foundation for obtaining a deeper insight of the key factors that could be impacting the overall success of the business.

General Environment

The company's business environment is competitive and always changing, understanding the general environmental factors is important to achieve success. General environmental analysis helps companies to recognize new opportunities, anticipate risks, and plan effective strategies. One method of analysis is through 7 Segments Analysis. In 7 Segments analysis, various key external factors, namely political, economic, sociological, technological, legal and environmental so that they influence an organization. It can also be used in a variety of different scenarios, and can guide professional people and senior managers in strategic decision making (Achadi et al., 2023).

Quoted from a journal written by (Kirana et al., 2023) that 7 Segments analysis is a systematic approach applied in business management and strategic planning to gain an understanding of external macro factors that can influence a particular organization, company or project. The acronym 7 Segments describes six main categories of external factors, namely: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal. The 7 Segments analysis process involves collecting data and evaluating each of these categories to understand their impact on the business or organization in question. It aims to help organizations design better strategies, identify business opportunities, manage risks and respond to environmental changes more effectively.

Porter's Five Forces Model

Porter's five forces model analysis has fundamental advantages in developing winning strategies in the industry. In an industry, persistent competition can determine the return on equity of an investment capital, which is determined by the return on equity of that capital investment. competitive or what is referred to as the basic rate of return in an industry known in economics as a perfectly competitive industry (Meftahudin et al., 2019). This involves analysis of the following things: Threat of New Entrants, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Bargaining Power of Buyers, Threat of Substitute Products, and Similar Competitors. Porter's five forces analysis is used to examine the external context of a company, focusing on competition between similar competitors, threats from the entry of new competitors, potential substitute products, bargaining power of buyers, and bargaining power of suppliers. This helps in evaluating the company's position in the market and identifying potential risks and opportunities that may arise.

Competitor Analysis

Competitor Analysis also known as the competitive analysis, is the process of identifying weak points in an industry and reviewing the various business strategies they employ. This information is used as a basis for comparison to identify the advantages and

disadvantages of the companies owned by the company's owner when compared to each other. Quoted from Adom et al., (2019) that competition is one of the most unavoidable forces in today's business world. The competitor analysis would involve several parameters such as Assumption, Objective, Strategy and Capability.

No matter whether the company is big or small, it has competitors in the industry and the strategies of these competitors influence the process of formulating strategic plans. Competition is an accepted feature of corporate life by profit-oriented organizations. Analyzing an organization's competitors helps to find its weaknesses as well as identify opportunities and threats from the industry environment. When formulating an organization's strategy, managers must consider the various strategies of the organization's competitors. Competitor analysis is a driver of organizational strategy and influences how a company acts or reacts in its industry. Organizations conduct competitor analysis to measure and/or assess their standing among competitors.

Internal Analysis

Internal analysis will be carried out through resources which includes Tangible factor such as Financial, Organization, Technology, Facility, Human Resource, Innovation and Reputation). The second is the Value-chain activity which involves primary data such as Inbound logistics, operation, outbound logistics, marketing and sales). Another point is The VRIO analysis which plays a crucial role in evaluating the internal resources and capabilities of the company based on four elements: Value, Rarity, Imitability and Organization which become the strategic framework systematically. This VRIO model is used to assess whether the certain resources in a company are strengths or weaknesses. The VRIO framework is structured to include a series of questions about a company's business activities, such as value, rarity, likelihood of imitation, and organization. The answers to these questions will determine whether a company's resources or capabilities are strengths or weaknesses.

The Resource Based View (RBV) analysis theory is a dynamic one that includes the capability life cycle (CLC). The capability lifecycle concept is a profound innovation in explaining the general pattern of development of organizational capabilities based on dynamic resource theory over time. RBV analysis highlights that competitive advantages based on resources and capabilities will last longer in the business journey than those that depend solely on product or market position. The resources in question can be financial, labor, physical facilities, and intangible assets (knowledge). The RBV concept really emphasizes the importance of resources and capabilities that are unique, valuable, and difficult to imitate in order to create competitive advantage (Muharam, 2019). Other Internal analysis which is required is the after service and support including the firm infrastructure, human resource management, technology development and procurement process.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a type of qualitative research that aims to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects, such as behavior, perceptions, motivations and actions holistically, by describing them in the form of descriptions using words and language, in a natural context and by utilizing various natural methods. It is hoped that all data collected can provide in-depth insight into the topics that have been researched.

Researchers will use a qualitative approach to explain business analysis using internal and external approaches, namely through information obtained directly from within the company. This research aims to produce relevant solutions for future steps that can be taken by companies. The research method that will be used in this research is the case study method. The purpose of a case study is to study real-world situations, developing situations, and interactions with the environment that occur within any social unit, such as an individual, group, organization, or community. Studying case studies may cover the entire life cycle or concentrate only on relevant segments.

The Qualitative data includes respondents' actions and words, personal documents, and survey data. This type of data allows researchers to conduct a more in-depth analysis of private hospitals. Primary data refers to information obtained passively from research subjects, similar to the results of research using previously established instruments. In this research, primary data was obtained through interviews with sources from sales and private hospital employees.

An interview is a type of question and answer that is conducted with a specific purpose. It involves two parties: the asker (interviewer) who asks the question and the answer provider (interviewee) who provides feedback on the question. Researchers used semi-structured interview techniques. The aim of this type of interview is to reveal problems more openly, where the interviewees are asked to provide their opinions and ideas (Machfudi et al., 2019).

During interviews, researchers must listen carefully and note down what the interviewee says. In this research, the researcher applied purposive sampling, where the selection of informants was based on special considerations, such as the informant's expertise in the research topic or their position which could make it easier for the researcher to understand the object or social situation being studied. To obtain the insight from the market, author will use the primary data collection through conducting in depth interview with customers using the 7P aspects. After gathering all of the information, author will use those data to gain insight what informants thought, behave and experience about the oncology medical devices from PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The general environment is reviewed using 7 segments (Political/Legal, Sociocultural, Economic, Demography, Physical, Global and Technology)

Political/Legal

Regulatory compliance and healthcare policies impact pricing and product approval in the Indonesian market. The Indonesian market is subject to specific healthcare regulations (based on PERKA BAPETEN No 3 Tahun 2021), that companies must comply with to operate. These regulations can affect the approval process for new medical devices, requiring the medical company to meet safety and efficacy standards. Non-compliance can result in fines, legal actions, and product bans. Indonesia's new regulations to strengthen healthcare facilities, including oncology, have become important, alongside heart disease, stroke, and uro-nephrology (Kemenkes 2023). On December 13th, 2023, the Asian Development Bank announced the approval of a \$650 million investment loan for public health labs and primary care facilities in Indonesia, part of the Primary Healthcare and Public Health Laboratories Upgrading and Strengthening (PLUS) project. Compliance with national and international regulations designed to minimize environmental impact is essential.

Sociocultural

Indonesia has seen a rise in cancer incidence due to aging population, lifestyle changes, and environmental factors (Cancer Globocan, 2023). Common types include breast, cervical, and lung cancers. The increasing cancer population drives demand for advanced oncology medical devices, essential for accurate diagnosis, effective treatment, and patient monitoring. Ensuring patient comfort during treatment enhances their experience and quality of life, critical for adherence to treatment plans and psychological well-being. Hospital reputation plays a significant role in attracting patients, building trust, and maintaining a competitive edge.

Economic

Economic conditions affect hospital budgets and purchasing power, leading to price sensitivity. Hospitals often rely on government funding, which can be influenced by economic conditions. During economic stress, governments may reduce healthcare budgets, impacting hospital revenues. Private hospitals focus more on cost-efficiency during economic downturns, opting for generic drugs, lower-cost suppliers, and bulk purchasing discounts. Due to a lack of infrastructure and funding in Indonesia's healthcare system (Economic Healthcare Reuters, 2023), many Indonesians travel abroad for medical treatment, especially to Singapore and Malaysia,

costing over US\$6 billion annually (Lipps, 2022). However, the pandemic and subsequent travel restrictions have forced Indonesians to turn to local hospitals, prompting the government to improve the regulatory landscape to attract more investment and improve the industry's outlook.

Demography

The demography impact of the oncology and radiation-based medical devices spans from manufacturing to disposal. Key concerns include resource consumption, energy use, chemical and radioactive waste, and compliance with regulatory standards. Addressing these issues involves adopting green manufacturing practices, improving energy efficiency, and implementing sustainable operations in healthcare facilities. Innovations in eco-friendly materials and recycling processes play a critical role in mitigating the environmental impact.

Physical

The number and distribution of specialized oncology centers impact access to cancer treatment. Urban areas like Jakarta often have more advanced facilities than rural regions, influencing patient access to specialized care. The capacity and quality of hospitals and clinics, including the availability of advanced medical equipment like MRI machines and radiotherapy units, are essential for effective cancer diagnosis and treatment.

Global

Indonesia may adopt international standards and protocols for cancer treatment and patient care, influenced by global best practices. This can enhance the quality and consistency of oncology services. International organizations and global health initiatives often focus on cancer prevention, treatment, and research. Partnerships with these organizations can bring in funding, expertise, and resources to improve cancer care in Indonesia.

Technological

Technological advancements in medical devices enhance diagnostic accuracy, improve treatment outcomes, ensure patient safety, facilitate transparent communication, and improve the overall patient experience. These factors contribute to building and sustaining customer/patient trust in hospitals. By investing in cutting-edge technologies and demonstrating a commitment to high-quality, patient-centered care, hospitals can enhance their reputation and foster long-term trust with their patients. The use of advanced technologies often leads to recognition by accrediting bodies and health organizations. This is very important to ensure only advanced equipments are allowed to be accepted in Indonesia market.

Porter Five Forces Analysis

Porter Five Forces	Level of Force	Explanation	Mitigation Strategies
Threat of New Entrants	High	New Competitors entering the market	Strengthen the installed base, securing existing channels, and potential future customers. Secure patents and intellectual property rights to prevent replication.
Bargaining Power of Suppliers	Low	There are many suppliers for medical device components. reducing their bargaining power	Create differentiation and innovation, Provide value added services, Build loyalty programmes for the long term contracts with customer
Threat of Substitute Products	High	Alternative brands offer similar quality at lower price, increasing the threat of substitutes	Enhance product differentiation, Build customer loyalty and provide more competitive pricing strategies

Bargaining Power of Buyers	High	Hospital can switch to cheaper options due to the price sensitive, hence it increases their bargaining power	Build strong relationships, offer bundled services and provide the value-added features
Rivalry Among Existing Competitors	High	Some competitors offer similar products at competitive prices which can intensify rivalry	Innovation-focused, competitive pricing, marketing strategies, and maintaining high quality standards

Competitor Analysis

According to the informant from PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia, there are two major competitors : PT Sehat Operations Indonesia and PT Unity Indonesia Sehat. Below are the conclusion for the competitor analysis. Based on the Assumption, Objective, Strategy and Capability (AOSC), it can be concluded that both competitor are very aggressive with their own unique capabilities and objectives to expand their market in Indonesia.

PT Sehat Operations Indonesia

Assumption	The company with long experience in Indonesia, which provides a wide range of medical equipment from medical imaging, monitoring, diagnostic, and oncology devices.
Objectives	To gain Indonesia market share with cheaper prices, and also supported with more flexible payment terms to customer
Strategy	To penetrate market with strong relationships and market distribution network across Indonesia. Offer clinical training to medical professionals to learn about their recent technology
Capability	The company offers strong connection to relevant stakeholders in the market. This company also has established strong partnership with local distributor in Indonesia with great reputation.

PT Unity Indonesia Sehat

Assumption	This company demand for advanced medical imaging technology with a wide range of medical equipment. However, in the market, it is still perceived as a newcomer with a few installed bases.
Objectives	The goal of this company is to become a leading provider of medical equipmeny in Indonesia , and to increase their profitability through selling the equipment and service contracts
Strategy	The company offers wide range of medical devices including radiology equipment. They are focus on building relationship with key stakeholders in healthcare sector, attending the industry conferences as well as offer training and education programs for healthcare professionals in Indoneia. From product pricing, they offer similar products with competitive pricing
Capability	The company offers financial strength among competitors while other healthcare vendor may have limited budgets. This company also has established strong research and development capabilities and already hired some professionals worker from other healthcare providers to equip their company better in the field.

Internal Analysis

Resource Based Value Analysis

Tangible Resources	
Physical Assets	PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia has one office in Indonesia
Equipment	High-tech machinery used in the manufacturing processes of products such as medical imaging equipment, oncology equipment, etc
Technological Assets	Advanced technologies used in the manufacturing process, to ensure high efficiency and quality
Financial Asset	Financial investment in other companies, joint ventures and strategic partnerships
Products	Oncology products such as PET/CT, SPECT/CT, Linear Accelerator and CT Simulator
Intangible Resources	
Intellectual Property	PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia holds numerous patents for its innovations in various fields such as energy, healthcare and automation
Human Resources	PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia holds highly skilled employees including engineers, researchers and technicians
Organizational Capabilities	Siemens uses a matrix organizational structure that allows for efficient collaboration across different functions and regions. This ensures that expertise and resources are effectively utilized across the company.
Innovation	PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia focus more on R&D, leading into continuous innovation and development of new products and solutions

VRIO Analysis

Resource or capability	Valuable	Rare	Costly to Imitate	Organized
Reputable Corporate Image	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Diversified Brand Portfolio	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
High Quality Product	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Technological Advancement and Digital Advancement	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Reputable Corporate Image

PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia is considered as reputable corporate which can attract customers, investors, and partners, enhancing overall business performance. However, while valuable, a reputable corporate image is not rare as many companies can achieve this through effective strategies. From the competition itself, building a strong reputation takes years of consistent performance and substantial investment, making it difficult for competitors to replicate quickly. The company itself is structured in a way to leverage its reputation for competitive advantage.

Diversified Brand Portfolio

PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia possess a diversified brand portfolio to reduce the risk and capitalizes on different market Segments, enhancing revenue streams. Not all companies have the resources or strategic capability to manage a diversified brand portfolio effectively. However, to make it well, the company is advised to better organized to manage and capitalize on the diversified portfolio for strategic advantage.

High-Quality Product

In terms of valuability, PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia possess high-quality products to meet customer needs and can command premium prices. And there are not many companies able to produce similar high-quality products. For some competitors, Achieving and maintaining high product quality can be costly in terms of R&D, quality control, and production processes.

Technological and Digital Advancement

PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia focuses to the technological and digital advancements to streamline operations, reduce costs, and improve customer experiences. The Cutting-edge technology produced by PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia can be rare and provide a significant competitive edge. To organize much better, the company is structured to integrate and leverage technological advancements effectively.

Value Chain Activity

Value Chain Analysis is a strategic tool used to analyze the internal activities of a firm to understand how they contribute to creating value for customers. There are two activities from the value chain, namely the primary activity which consists of the inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales, and after services. The second part is related to the support activities which covers the firm infrastructure, human resource management, technology development, and procurement. After reviewing the Value Chain Analysis of PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia, here is the conclusion of Value Chain Analysis which consist of primary activities and support activities :

Primary Activities:

- **Inbound Logistics:** The company manages a robust supplier network and advanced inventory systems to ensure timely delivery of high-quality materials without overstocking.
- **Operations:** Utilizes advanced manufacturing processes and technologies for medical products, emphasizing R&D for continuous innovation.
- **Outbound Logistics:** Maintains a global distribution network and multiple warehouses to ensure efficient product delivery.
- **Marketing and Sales:** Invests in brand management, has a dedicated sales force, and employs digital marketing strategies to reach a wider audience.
- **After Service:** Provides comprehensive customer support, including installation, maintenance, and training, to build long-term relationships.

Support Activities:

- **Firm Infrastructure:** Features a well-defined management structure and strong corporate governance, enhancing operational efficiency and investor confidence.
- **Human Resource Management:** Focuses on talent acquisition, continuous training, and fostering a positive work environment.
- **Technology Development:** Invests in R&D and robust IT systems to support business operations and drive innovation.
- **Procurement:** Implements stringent supplier selection and efficient cost management practices.

Customer Analysis

According to Keller (2013), understanding target customers is crucial because different customers have varying brand knowledge, perceptions, and preferences. The research conducted an analysis of customer profiles, considering demographic, geographical, and behavioral factors. The respondents were aged 29 to 54 years, with a gender split of 40% female and 60% male. They held roles such as Senior Procurement Team members, COOs, General Managers, Hospital Owners, Procurement Specialists, and Doctors, with experience ranging from 5 to 30 years. The respondents were from private hospitals in Jakarta, Pekanbaru, and Bandung, primarily Type A and B hospitals, and were focusing on expanding oncology services. While the product was perceived as high quality, it was also considered expensive by most informants.

SWOT Analysis

<p>Strength</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High quality products with a long history footprint in Indonesia and well-known by customers • Elegant Design • Established brand worldwide • Supported by knowledgeable employees 	<p>Weakness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High price compared to competitors • Complicated purchasing process • Slow response from engineers • Limited advertisement visibility
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Expansion in aging populations with higher chances of cancer cases • Improve after-sales service • Enhance digital marketing and participation to medical exhibitions 	<p>Threat</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong competition with lower prices • Economic constraint on hospital budgets, especially in private hospitals • Regulatory changes affecting the price

V. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The research findings highlight several key factors influencing the selection of oncology medical devices by private hospitals in Indonesia. Internally, the quality of the products, pricing strategies, purchasing processes, and after-sales services are major concerns for informants. Externally, regulatory compliance, government initiatives to allocate hospital budgets for oncology equipment, and the rising incidence of cancer are significant factors. These external factors underscore the need for advanced medical devices that offer accurate diagnoses, effective treatment, and patient comfort. Based on the fact mentioned above, author will give proposed marketing strategy to PT Sehat Healthcare Indonesia: Enhance Product Differentiation (Product), Improve After Sales Support (Product), Pricing Strategy (Pricing) To support customers especially for those who are struggling with their internal finance scheme, Establish regular event participation (Promotion)

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